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Classification of Trick Shots in Rocket League Using Machine Learning

RLSA

Data Management Plan (DMP)

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Deliverable abstract

This deliverable is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Rocket League Skillshot Analysis project. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles outlined in the FAIR Data section.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

CONTRIBUTORS

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#).

Pelka Thimon (e12123690@student.tuwien.ac.at, ORCID: 0009-0007-3411-5702) will act as the data manager who will be in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

1.2. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Rocket League Skillshot Collection Training Set	Structured text	csv	100 - 1000 MB	no
P2	Rocket League Skillshot Collection Test Set	Structured text	csv	100 - 1000 MB	no
P3	Rocket League Skillshot Collection Validation Set	Structured text	csv	100 - 1000 MB	no

Description for "Rocket League Skillshot Collection Training Set":

Training Set for RL Skillshot Data

Description for "Rocket League Skillshot Collection Test Set":

Test Split for RL Skillshot data

Description for "Rocket League Skillshot Collection Validation Set":

Validation Split for RL Skillshot data

1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The research data was generated by the Tutors of the Machine Learning Task this was taken from. The data collection itself is not part of the Project. The machine learning part was accomplished using the sklearn python library which simplifies machine learning tasks by offering complete models which you can easily run on a variety of data. The data preprocessing was done using pandas and numpy.

After preprocessing the data is split into a train, validation and test split. The train split is used for training the model, the validation split is used for the validation of hyperparameter tuning and the test split is used for final evaluation of the model.

1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users

Students participating in DAST 2025S UE.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

We will make our data findable by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier and adding relevant metadata. The repository will provide means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation.

The dataset is structured to facilitate both human and machine readability, adhering to the FAIR principles. Each goal event in the dataset is represented by a sequence of 30 frames, capturing detailed information such as ball speed, location, rotation, player speed, position, rotation, and input actions. The data is organized in a tabular format, with each row corresponding to a frame and each column representing a specific feature. To

ensure proper versioning, a systematic version control strategy. Each iteration of the dataset and associated analysis scripts is assigned a unique version identifier, following semantic versioning conventions (e.g., v1.0.0). Changes between versions are documented in a changelog, detailing modifications, additions, or deletions. This approach facilitates traceability and reproducibility of our research. The dataset and related materials are stored in TU Wien's internal test DBRepo instance, which provides persistent identifiers (DOIs) for each version, ensuring long-term accessibility and citability.

We will be using the following domain specific metadata standards: Each dataset contains metadata about title, creators, affiliation, abstract, keywords, license and a DOI. This will help others to identify, discover, and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, descriptions, or keywords when publishing data. In this case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow interdisciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?
- Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Data:

- Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.
- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
- If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Metadata:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests. Some datasets cannot be published and even need to be deleted at the end of the project. See section 5 for more details.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	No	2025-04-28	TU Wien Research Data	10.82556/myw9-yb20	CC-BY-4.0
P2	Open	No	2025-04-28	TU Wien Research Data	10.82556/a3xv-7310	CC-BY-4.0
P3	Open	No	2025-04-28	TU Wien Research Data	10.82556/ad45-4983	CC-BY-4.0

Repository description:

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it.
<https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: Users who want to completely run the entire software only need python installed (preferably a version >3.11) and the required libraries which are documented in a requirements.txt file.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use

within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow re-using, refining, or extending them?
- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain. As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions will include details on the methodology used, analytical, and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked. The digital research data obtained will be published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided that there are no data protection concerns.

Detailed documentation is provided alongside the dataset to support validation and reuse: - A comprehensive readme file describing the purpose of the dataset, data structure, and file contents - A data dictionary defining each variable, its units, possible values, and meaning - A description of the data pre-processing steps, including any transformations or filtering applied - Information about the machine learning models developed (including hyperparameter tuning process) is documented in the uploaded python notebook which also contains the code for running the entire machine learning process. - A general reference to the software scripts and tools used for the data

preprocessing and model training. This documentation ensures that external users can validate the analyses conducted and independently replicate or extend the work.

The following data quality checks will be done: data entry validation and representation with controlled vocabularies.

3. Other research outputs

- In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).
- Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

In addition to data, this project generates several **digital research outputs** including:

- Python source code (contained in Jupyter Notebooks and associated scripts)
- Machine learning models (.pkl serialized model files)
- Workflow documentation for data preprocessing, model training, and evaluation
- Hyperparameter optimization protocols
- Prediction outputs (e.g., confusion matrices, classification reports)

The models, confusion matrices and reports are deposited to TUWRD:

ID	title	Type/format	DOI
O1	<i>best_model_decision_tree_classifier.pkl</i> Best Decision Tree Model generated by Script	Pickle	10.70124/jcjbz-nyc08
O2	<i>best_model_random_forst_classifier.pkl</i> Best Random FOrrest Model generated by Script	Pickle	10.70124/jcjbz-nyc08
O3	<i>confusion_matrix_decision_tree_classifier.png</i> Confusion Matrix for the best decision tree classifier	Image/png	10.70124/jcjbz-nyc08
O4	<i>confusion_matrix_random_forest_classifier.png</i> Confusion Matrix for the best random forest classifier	Image/png	10.70124/jcjbz-nyc08

ID	title	Type/format	DOI
O5	<i>rocketskillshots_test_predicted.csv</i> CSV file containing the prediction for each goal of the test data	csv	10.70124/jcjbz-nyc08

Management and FAIR Compliance:

All digital outputs will be managed following the FAIR principles:

- **Findability:**
 Each output will be described with appropriate metadata (e.g., author, creation date, version, purpose) and deposited in institutional repositories (e.g., TUWRD for results and DBRepo for data). Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), such as DOIs, will be assigned to enable stable referencing and citation.
- **Accessibility:**
 Research outputs will be made accessible via the repositories with controlled access where necessary (e.g., for sensitive model outputs). Open licenses (e.g., MIT License for source code) will be used whenever possible to ensure reusability, while respecting intellectual property and data protection requirements.
- **Interoperability:**
 Outputs such as source code and models will use widely recognized formats (e.g., .ipynb, .py, .pkl, .csv) and standards. Code will comply with Python community standards (PEP8) and include a clear requirements.txt for reproducibility. Metadata standards (such as DataCite schema) will be used where appropriate.
- **Reusability:**
 Outputs will be accompanied by comprehensive documentation including a README file, detailed comments within the code, descriptions of input/output formats, and data dictionaries where applicable. This ensures that other researchers can reproduce, verify, and build upon the work without additional clarifications.
 Where possible, outputs will be synchronized with external metadata hubs (e.g., OpenAIRE, BASE) through TUWRD to further maximize their visibility and impact. Updated versions of outputs will be versioned transparently, following best practices to ensure traceability of changes.

4. Allocation of resources

- What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
- How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
- Who will be responsible for data management in your project?
- How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

The data manager will direct the data management process overall, with Pelka Thimon being responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

5. Data security

- What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
- Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

5.1. Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by Thimon Pelka (acting as the person responsible for data management and DMP) in cooperation with the system operator. The data will be stored on TU Wien servers.

P1 (Rocket League Skillshot Collection Training Set), P2 (Rocket League Skillshot Collection Test Set), P3 (Rocket League Skillshot Collection Validation Set) will be stored on the test instance of DBRepo.

5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies.

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P1	TU Wien Database Repository	10 years
P2	TU Wien Database Repository	10 years
P3	TU Wien Database Repository	10 years

6. Ethical and legal issues

- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

6.1. Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

6.2. Intellectual property rights and rights of use

The following individual(s) hold rights and control access to the project data: The data used in this project is supposed to only be used by students within the project. These students only have read rights for the given database. Of course they can copy the data and setup a separate database themselves.

6.3. Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

7. Other issues

- Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

No